

Synthesis and Pharmacology of some 2-[3-(4-Aryl-1-piperazinyl)propyl]-1*H*-benz[de]isoquinolin-1,3(2*H*)-diones/2,5-pyrrolidinediones

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OUR continued interest in ω -aminoalkyl imides (1) led to the preparation of a number of *N*-[ω -(4-aryl-1-piperazinyl)alkyl]imides (2) and their pharmacological evaluation¹⁻³. These compounds show varying degree of CNS depressant activity.

During these studies it was noted that the pharmacological activity was governed by the nature of the three moieties present in the basic pharmacophore (1), namely, the imide part, the alkylene bridge and the terminal amine residue. It was found that the chain length of the alkylene bridge and the nature of the imide part were crucial for the activity. Propylene chain was ideal for the CNS depressant activity. Moreover, it is a known fact that lipophilicity—lipophobicity balance is one of the important parameters for the desired activity. Increase in the lipophilicity of a drug may increase the activity due to better crossing of the blood-brain barrier. With these things in mind, 2-[3-(4-aryl-1-piperazinyl)propyl]-1*H*-benz[de]isoquinolin-1,3(2*H*)-diones (3) which contained a bulky lipophilic naphthalimide as the imide part were prepared. Some similar naphthalimides have been recently reported to have antidepressant⁴, antiinflammatory⁴, local anaesthetic⁵, cytostatic⁶ and rhodenticidal⁷ activities. Succinimide, being the simplest imide, a parallel series of 1-3-(4-aryl-1-piperazinyl)propyl-2,5-pyrrolidinediones (4) was also prepared.

1-Substitutedphenylpiperazines (5) were heated with acrylonitrile to obtain 4-aryl-1-(2-cyanoethyl)piperazines (6) which were reduced catalytically to the corresponding 4-aryl-1-(3-aminopropyl)piper-

azines⁸ (7). 7 were subsequently condensed with the appropriate anhydrides to obtain the title compounds (3 and 4).

Pharmacology :

All the compounds showed mild sedative action in mice. However, it did not warrant further screening. These compounds, however, showed promising hypotensive activity. Cats of either sex, weighing between 2.5-4 kg were anaesthetised by i.p. injection of urethane (400 mg/kg) and chloralose (50 mg/kg). The trachea was exposed and cannulated. The cannula was connected to Mary's Tambur for recording respiration. Left common carotid artery was cannulated and the cannula was connected to a mercury manometer for recording B.P. The test compounds were injected in the form of their aqueous solutions of their hydrochloride salts, i.v., at the dose of 0.5-1.0 mg/kg. All the compounds showed good hypotensive activity in normotensive cats and the onset of action was quick. 4 showed fall in B.P. of about 80-100 mm of Hg with duration of action about 30 min. 3 were found to lower the B.P. by about 60-80 mm of Hg; however, the duration of action was only about 5-10 min. Within each series variations in the activity with respect to the substituents were marginal.

Experimental

All melting points reported are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Beckmann Acculab-10 spectrophotometer. Pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian-60 spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard. 1-Arylpiperazines (5) were prepared by the Pollard method⁸. Reaction of 5 with acrylonitrile and subsequent reduction of the cyanocompounds (6) to the corresponding amino derivatives (7) is known⁹.

1-[3-(4-(4-Methylphenyl)-1-piperazinyl)propyl]-2,5-pyrrolidinedione.HCl (4d) : 7d (2.32 g, 0.01 mol) and succinic anhydride (1.0 g, 0.01 mol) were refluxed in dry pyridine (30 ml) for 10 h. Acetic anhydride (5 ml) was added and the mixture was further refluxed for 5 h. The solution was concentrated *in vacuo* and the residue was taken in ethanol (50 ml). The solution was filtered and dry HCl gas was passed through the solution when the hydrochloride of the product separated out. The solution was cooled and filtered. The product was crystallised from ethanol (2.3 g, 60%), m.p. 221-22; ν_{max} (KBr) 1690 and 1760 cm^{-1} (CONCO); δ (D_2O) 2.0 (2H, m, $NCH_2CH_2CH_2N$), 2.22 (3H, s, $PhCH_3$), 2.64 (4H, s, $COCH_2CH_2CO$), 3.2-3.66 (12H, m, $N(CH_2)_2CH_2N$, $NCH_2CH_2CH_2N$) and 6.82-7.3 (4H, dd, J 9 Hz, ArH).

Compounds 4a-g were prepared similarly by condensing succinic anhydride with appropriate 7 (Table 1)

TABLE 1—1-[3-(4-SUBSTITUTED-PHENYL-1-PIPERAZINYL)-PROPYL]-2,5-PYRROLIDINEDIONES HCl (4)*

Compd no.	R	Yield %	M p. °C
4a	H	65	237-38
4b	2- CH_3	58	217-18
4c	3- CH_3	58	245-46
4d	4- CH_3	60	221-22
4e	2-Cl	55	198-99
4f	3-Cl	55	213-14
4g	4-Cl	59	238-39

* Showed satisfactory elemental analyses.

2-[3-(4-(4-Methylphenyl)-1-piperazinyl)propyl]-1H-benz[de]isoquinolin-1,3(2H)dione(3d) : 7d (2.32 g, 0.01 mol) and naphthalic anhydride (1.98 g, 0.01 mol) were heated in an oil-bath at 160-70° for 1 h. The mixture was cooled and the oily residue boiled in ethanol when a yellow solid separated. The solution was cooled and filtered. The residue was crystallised from CH_2Cl_2 -petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) (70 : 30, v/v), (2.7 g, 70%), m.p. 140-41°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1650 and 1695 (CONCO); δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.9 (2H, m, $NCH_2CH_2CH_2N$), 2.25 (3H, s, $PhCH_3$), 2.56 (6H, m, $CH_2N(CH_2)_2$), 2.9 (4H, t, ArN(CH_2)₂),

TABLE 2—2-[3-(4-SUBSTITUTED-PHENYL-1-PIPERAZINYL)-PROPYL]-1H-BENZ[de]ISOQUINOLIN-1,3(2H)-DIONES (3)*

Compd. no.	R	Yield %	M p. °C
3a	H	75	142-43
3b	2- CH_3	70	145-46
3c	3- CH_3	60	115-16
3d	4- CH_3	70	140-41
3e	2-Cl	65	150-51
3f	3-Cl	65	98-99
3g	4-Cl	69	143-44

* Showed satisfactory elemental analyses.

4.22 (2H, t, $CH_2N(CO)_2$), 6.7 and 7.0 (4H, dd, J 8 Hz, *p*- $CH_3C_6H_4$) and 7.5-8.6 (6H, m, naphth-H)

Compounds 3a-g were prepared similarly by condensing naphthalic anhydride with appropriate 7 (Table 2).

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Chemical Examination of *Nymphaea stellata* Willd

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NYMPHAEA stellata Willd. (Nymphaeaceae)¹⁻³, popularly known as *Chit-shaluk* or *Sapla*, grows abundantly in the hotter parts of India. The plant is medicinally very important and its flower has an acrid, cooling, bitter-sweetish taste and is used in removing impurities from the blood. A decoction of flowers is prescribed in the palpitation of heart. The powdered root-stock is used as body strengthening medicine, hair-tonic and in the treatment of dyspepsia diarrhoea and piles. Survey of literature reveals that no phytochemical work seems to have been done on this plant. Accordingly, a chemical investigation of the aerial parts (leaves and stems) of this plant has been undertaken.

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